

Building resilience of the Ghanaian healthcare system: Lessons from a global health stage: Preparedness for the next pandemic: A Scoping Review

Martin Ankomah¹, Patience Aseweh Abor^{2*}, Humphrey Karamagi³

¹Department of Health Services Management, University of Ghana Business School, University of Ghana, Legon-Accra, Ghana

Email: matankomah@yahoo.com

²Department of Health Services Management, University of Ghana Business School, University of Ghana, Legon-Accra, Ghana

Email: pabor@ug.edu.gh

³Office of the Assistant Regional Director I Regional Office for Africa, Djoue | Brazzaville | Congo

Email: karamagih@who.int

*** Correspondence:**

Patience A. Abor

pabor@ug.edu.gh

Abstract

Background: The coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic has underscored the need for resilient health systems. However, Ghana does not seem to achieve commensurate results, suggesting potential gaps in critical interventions. This study examines these gaps by drawing on global experiences to guide Ghana's preparedness for future emergencies.

Methods: A scoping review based on the synthesis of published journal articles and grey literature was used to gather relevant evidence to address the study's objective. Peer-reviewed literature searches were conducted in databases, including Medline, Scopus, and Health Sources, supplemented by searches on organizational websites to identify grey literature. We adopted the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) framework to explore how health systems responded to the COVID-19 pandemic globally and draw lessons for strengthening Ghana's health system resilience. We analyzed policy responses in three main areas: pandemic preparedness, crisis management, and response and recovery.

Results: Ten strategies emerged from the study as critical in strengthening health system resilience against future pandemics. These strategies include whole-of-government engagement, financing for preparedness, community engagement and trust, robust surveillance systems, emergency medical care, diverse workforce development, digital health integration, critical health infrastructure, well-planned commodities/products, and social capital. Each strategy plays a vital

role in enhancing preparedness, response, and recovery efforts, highlighting the multifaceted approach needed to mitigate the impact of future pandemics on health systems.

Conclusions: The identified strategies align with the attributes of a resilient healthcare system. By adopting these strategies, Ghana can build a resilient healthcare system that effectively addresses future challenges, guided by global insights and experiences.

Keywords: Health systems resilience, COVID-19 pandemic, global experiences, emergency preparedness, crisis management, response and recovery, Ghana's health system

Introduction

Globally, health systems face various public health risks and safety threats that impede progress toward achieving universal health coverage and health security goals (Emami *et al.*, 2023; Fridell *et al.*, 2020; Olu, 2017). Urgent action is advocated by the World Health Organization (WHO) to establish more robust health systems that can effectively anticipate and respond to health challenges (Ghebreyesus *et al.*, 2022; WHO, 2022a; 2022b).

The necessity for resilient health systems is underscored by past shocks, such as the H1N1 influenza, Ebola outbreaks, and Zika, which exposed vulnerabilities and emphasized the need for reform (Elston *et al.*, 2016; Kruk *et al.*, 2015; Olu, 2017; Tumusiime *et al.*, 2019). The recent COVID-19 pandemic has reinforced the critical importance of resilient health systems (Forsgren *et al.*, 2022; Haldane *et al.*, 2021; Karamagi *et al.*, 2022; Rajapaksha *et al.*, 2022). As a global pandemic, COVID-19 wreaked havoc on health systems, economies, and societies worldwide (WHO, 2021a; Yang *et al.*, 2021). It tested health systems globally, exposing gaps in emergency preparedness and response, even in systems previously deemed strong (El Bcheraoui *et al.*, 2020; Haldane *et al.*, 2021; Sagan *et al.*, 2021).

Ghana confirmed its first cases in March 2020, triggering a national emergency (Sarkodie *et al.*, 2021). Responding to the outbreak, Ghana adopted a coordinated, centralized approach under the Inter-Ministerial Coordinating Committee chaired by the President. The response centered on five themes: limiting virus importation, containment, care provision, socio-economic impact mitigation, and domestic capacity expansion (Ayee, 2022; Fenny & Otioku, 2020; Republic of Ghana, MOH, 2020a, 2020b, 2022; Sarkodie *et al.*, 2021).

Challenges such as shortages of personal protective equipment (PPE), testing limitations, delayed test results, and staffing inadequacies initially hindered Ghana's COVID-19 management (Osei-Boateng & Vlaminc, 2021; World Bank, 2020; Sarkodie *et al.*, 2021). Policy measures were implemented, including travel restrictions, public gathering bans, closure of schools, relief packages, healthcare worker support, infrastructure enhancement, and vaccination campaigns. Preventive strategies included handwashing, mask mandates, and social distancing, supported by the media and helplines (Issahaku & Abu, 2020; Osei-Boateng & Vlaminc, 2021). The Ghana Health Service (GHS) collaborated across agencies outside the health sector, enhancing contact tracing, testing, and surveillance. Other strategic efforts involved local production of PPE, expanding testing through public and private labs, expanding infrastructure, converting facilities to treatment centers, and increasing bed capacity. The funding was diverse, including the World

Bank and other development partners, NGOs, and private donations to the COVID-19 trust funds (Antwi-Boasiako *et al.*, 2021; Ayee, 2022; Fenny *et al.*, 2016; Sarkodie *et al.*, 2021). However, concerns were raised regarding adherence to safety protocols and transparency in vaccine procurement (Ayee, 2022).

Risk communication and social mobilization strategies included presidential broadcasts, press briefings, and message dissemination through media and helplines. Case management involved isolation at treatment centers or home isolation supported by protocols, staff training, and infrastructure expansion. To address infrastructure challenges, Ghana initiated "Agenda 111," aiming to build hospitals in underserved districts (Antwi-Boasiako *et al.*, 2021; Issahaku & Abu, 2020; Republic of Ghana, MOH, 2021a; Sarkodie *et al.*, 2021).

Despite progress, Ghana's health system resilience remains insufficient for potential emergencies (Asiedu-Berkoe *et al.*, 2022; Ayee, 2022; Republic of Ghana, MOH, 2020c). Shortages persist in infrastructure, equipment, and skilled personnel for emergency care leading to exhaustion of healthcare providers and patient care challenges (Yevo *et al.*, 2023). Despite improvements in the health workforce, significant shortages remain, especially in critical areas such as surgery, obstetrics, trauma, and anesthesia care (Jumbam *et al.*, 2022). Specialist gaps are evident, with only 24% of GHS hospitals having surgeons in 2018, and primary hospitals lacking essential specialists, such as pediatricians and psychiatrists (Asamani *et al.*, 2021; Asamani 2021; Jumbam *et al.*, 2022). Peripheral facilities struggle with emergency and non-emergency care as skilled professionals are concentrated in regional centers (Yevo *et al.* 2023). Limited IT integration, aging equipment, professional migration, and underfunded ambulance services further impede emergency care (Ankomah *et al.*, 2015; Republic of Ghana, MOH, 2021b; Okyere, 2018; Piersson & Gorleku, 2017)

Ghana's efforts to enhance resilience in the health system are evident. However, the country does not seem to achieve commensurate results, suggesting potential gaps in critical interventions. This study examines these gaps by drawing on global experiences to guide Ghana's preparedness for future emergencies. The principal aim of this study was to extract and synthesize global experience and learn valuable lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic to strengthen Ghana's health system resilience. Given the broad and exploratory nature of the objective and the need for a comprehensive approach, we chose a scoping review for this study. This methodology, known for its flexibility and inclusivity, enables thorough exploration and synthesis of diverse sources, aligning with the study's objectives (Anderson *et al.*, 2008; Levac *et al.*, 2010; Arksey & O'Malley, 2005).

Review question

This review sought to address the following research question: What are the critical gaps in Ghana's health system resilience, as evidenced by its response to the COVID-19 pandemic, and how can global experiences inform strategies to strengthen its preparedness for future emergencies?

The concept of health system resilience

Health system resilience is a vital concept that encompasses the capacity of health actors, institutions, and populations to effectively prepare for, respond to, and recover from crises and shocks, while maintaining essential functions and services (Kruk *et al.*, 2015). This concept has evolved to include strategies for minimizing exposure, managing risks, and addressing potential stressors, such as population aging (Paschoalotto *et al.*, 2023). Recent definitions of health system resilience emphasize proactive elements, encompassing anticipation, absorption, and adaptation to sudden shocks and structural changes, extending beyond acute events to encompass continuity in health improvement and the ability to respond effectively to emerging health needs (Grimm *et al.*, 2022; Karamagi *et al.* 2022; Sagan *et al.*, 2021). Despite various definitions, resilience in health systems is understood as the collective ability to mitigate, respond, and recover from disruptions, maintain essential services, and learn for improvement.

Methods

Analytical framework

The study adopted the OECD Framework to explore how health systems responded to COVID-19 on a global stage and the lessons that can be drawn to guide Ghana's efforts toward strengthening the resilience of its health system (OECD, 2022). The Framework focuses on three main policy responses corresponding to the different phases of the risk management cycle: pandemic preparedness, crisis management, and response and recovery (See Fig. 1 attached as Extended Data).

Pandemic preparedness involves anticipating and developing the capacity to respond to potential pandemics. It entails risk-anticipation capacities, critical sector preparedness, and pandemic management protocols. Crisis management refers to the policies and actions implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic. It involves risk-anticipation capacities, critical sector preparedness, and pandemic management protocols. Response and recovery are related to strategies to mitigate pandemic effects, support economic recovery, and protect vulnerable groups. These measures include lockdowns and restrictions to prevent the spread of the virus; financial assistance to households, companies, and markets to lessen the effects of the economic downturn; health initiatives to safeguard and treat the populace; and social initiatives to protect the most vulnerable groups.

Guided by this framework, this paper examined publications, reports, and policy documents related to the health system's resilient response to COVID-19 in three main thematic areas: preparedness, crisis management, and response and recovery.

Design

A scoping review based on the synthesis of published journal articles and grey literature was used to gather relevant evidence to address the research question. This approach allowed us to explore the extensive literature on the global response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The scoping review

process followed the methodological framework proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). In reporting the outcomes of the scoping review, we followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses for Scoping Review (PRISMA-ScR) checklist (See Fig. 2 attached as Extended Data) (Tricco et al., 2018)

Eligibility Criteria

The primary inclusion criteria were papers that were published in English and focused on health system resilience related to COVID-19. Other inclusions were papers that discussed strategies for health emergencies or pandemic preparedness and response. The exclusion criteria included papers not marched with the research design, papers unrelated to healthcare system resilience (e.g., climate, environment, food security), those solely focused on the delivery of health services without considering the broader health system, clinical trials, or protocols as well as disease-specific conditions other than COVID-19. To ensure that the literature was contemporary with the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic, papers published in English from 2020 onwards were considered.

Information Sources

Online searches were conducted from May to June 2023 for relevant journal articles and gray literature related to health system preparedness and response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Journal articles were accessed from Medline, Scopus, Health Sources, and WHO databases. Websites of national and local organizations and Google Advanced Search were used to search for grey literature.

Search strategy

We used the Joana Briggs Institute (JBI) three-step search process to identify records for the review (Peters et al., 2015). The search strategy was developed in consultation with, and refined based on input from a librarian. First, we conducted a preliminary search using Medline and Google Scholar to gather background information and identify previous studies relevant to our topic. The analysis of these materials and their reference lists guided the authors to include journal articles, policy briefs, commentaries, editorials, and reports in the review process. In the second step, the first two authors searched across all four included databases using the search strategy, which had been refined based on all identified keywords and index terms from the first step. In the third step, the reference list of all the identified papers and reports was searched for additional sources.

The search queries were structured at three levels. Level 1 included terms related to health system resilience, such as "resilient," "health system resilience," "coping COVID-19," "health system adaptation," and "health system preparedness." Level 2 terms focused on COVID-19, including "coronavirus," "COVID," "SARS-CoV-2," "COVID-19," "COVID-19 pandemic," and "COVID-19 response strategies." Level 3 terms denoted public health events, such as "health emergency," "health emergency preparedness," "health emergency response," "shock," and "health security." During the search, we employed Boolean operators such as AND/OR to combine the search terms. The search strategy included the application of truncation and wild cards to broaden the search.

Screening and selection process

The screening involved reviewing the title and abstract of papers identified for inclusion in the study. The first two authors independently screened the titles and abstracts to identify potential articles for full-text assessment. They then assessed the selected full-text articles to confirm that the studies met the inclusion criteria. Where necessary, the authors sought additional clarity regarding article eligibility from the third author, who served as an impartial arbitrator. We used the PRISMA flow diagram (Ankomah *et al.*, 2023) to show how the study progressed at each stage of the review process (See Figure 3 attached as Extended Data).

Data extraction

A [Microsoft Excel](#), version 2403, spreadsheet was used to systematically capture the characteristics from the included studies. These characteristics included the source (author(s) and year of publication) document type (articles and reviews, editorials and commentaries, conference and meeting reports, policy briefs), focus areas, and intervention (response strategies). Retrieved references were managed using [Mendeley Reference Manager](#), version 2.98.0. The elements in our analytical framework guided the process of data extraction. Given the exploratory nature of scoping reviews, we focused on mapping the existing literature. No critical evaluation of the quality of individual articles was done, as this is not part of the standard methodology of scoping reviews. All three authors independently charted the data to enhance reliability.

Data analysis and reporting

We adopted a thematic content analysis approach to analyze the data extracted from the literature review. We structured our data analysis and reporting using the OECD framework's main policy response areas: pandemic preparedness, crisis management, and response and recovery (See Figure 1 attached as Extended Data). Within this framework, we systematically analyzed each theme and its elements (sub-themes), identifying key areas of focus and synthesizing the strategies implemented. Additionally, we provided illustrative examples from various countries to showcase the diverse approaches adopted globally to address the COVID-19 pandemic. This approach allowed us to organize and present our findings in a structured and cohesive manner.

Results

The initial database searches yielded 1,788 online materials. After removing duplicates, 1,744 unique records proceeded to the title and abstract screening phase. Following this screening process, 305 records were left for full-text review. From these, 80 studies met the inclusion criteria as illustrated in Figure 2 attached as Extended Data.

The 80 publications retained for the analysis were published between January 2020 and June 2023. The majority of these documents consisted of original articles and reviews (n=71, 88.8%).

Editorials and commentaries constituted 3.8% (n=3), conference and meeting reports 2.5% (n=2), and policy briefs 5% (n=4) of the total.

Table 1 (attached as Extended Data) summarizes the results of the thematic analysis.

Global Health Systems Response to COVID-19 Pandemic

In the following paragraphs, we delve into the strategies implemented by various countries in addressing the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. These strategies are analyzed through the lens of the OCED's comprehensive framework encompassing three main domains: preparedness for emergencies, crisis management, and response and recovery.

Emergency preparedness

Emergency preparedness encompasses three sub-themes: disaster risk anticipation and foresight, emergency protocols, and preparedness of critical sectors (Table 1).

Disaster risk anticipation and foresight

Disaster risk anticipation and foresight involve understanding hazards, developing risk-assessment capacities, and employing response strategies (OECD, 2022). Risk and vulnerability assessments were noted to be crucial for preparedness and response in Ethiopia and Malawi during the COVID-19 pandemic (Lanyero et al., 2021; Mghamba et al., 2023). Robust surveillance systems with early detection mechanisms were effectively implemented in South Korea, Vietnam, Singapore, China, and Australia, leading to the timely implementation of containment measures (Chua et al., 2020; Sundararaman et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021; Williams, Fahy, et al., 2022). A comprehensive range of surveillance approaches, including case investigation, contact tracing, community-based initiatives, laboratory-based sentinel surveillance, serological studies, telephone hotlines, and genomic sequencing, also improved disease detection and response in Congo, Nigeria, Senegal, and Uganda (Okeke et al., 2022; Fawole et al., 2023).

Digital health tools such as Big Data in Singapore and Taiwan and the Surveillance Outbreaks Response Management and Analysis System (SORMAS) in Nigeria enhanced monitoring. China, Israel, India, South Korea, Singapore, Rwanda, and Tanzania employed GPS tracking, credit card records, surveillance videos, and mobile applications (Chang et al., 2020; Kuguyo et al., 2020; Mghamba et al., 2023; Okeke et al., 2022; X. Wang et al., 2021). European countries adapted digital health tools, such as France's "TousAntiCovid" app. New Zealand, Sweden, and the US used syndromic surveillance, while China, Fiji, India, Japan, and Vietnam utilized real-time reporting systems for COVID-19 cases (Haldane et al., 2021; Williams, Fahy, et al., 2022).

Data governance was vital; South Africa used epidemiological data for interventions (Moonasar et al., 2021) and the Eastern Mediterranean region employed collaborative surveillance (Abubakar et al., 2022). Investment in research and development contributed to preparedness, as exemplified by Rwanda, while Indonesia's health system foundations enabled proactive responses (Aisyah et al., 2022; Binagwaho et al., 2022). These examples emphasize the importance of risk assessment, surveillance, and digital technology in disaster response.

Emergency protocols

Emergency protocols provide a structured framework for coordinated responses during emergencies (OECD 2022). Countries, including Rwanda, Trinidad and Tobago, Iran, and Sri Lanka, developed national policies and guidelines for COVID-19 prevention, clinical tools, and healthcare provider guidelines to ensure an effective response (Dzinamarira et al., 2020; Gouya et al., 2023; Hunte et al., 2020; Mghamba et al., 2023). Ethiopia also developed comprehensive standards, guides, and protocols to effectively respond to the COVID-19 pandemic. These documents covered various aspects, such as quarantine, infection prevention and control, border control, case management, and home-based care (Lanyero et al., 2021; Zikargae, 2020).

Preparedness of critical sectors

The analysis revealed various strategies to enhance preparedness in critical sectors during the COVID-19 pandemic. These include maintaining strategic reserves of PPEs, ICU devices, consumables, and pharmaceuticals, optimizing supply chains and utilization protocols, and providing adequate healthcare professional training (Arabi et al., 2021; Williams, Fahy, et al., 2022). Public-private partnerships, research and development, and the continued use of digital health tools were also identified as crucial for building resilience and response capabilities during pandemics (Coccia, 2022). Additionally, improving the healthcare infrastructure, especially in the production and delivery of oxygen and therapeutics, was vital for better preparedness and management of future public health emergencies (Gebremeskel et al., 2021; Gouya et al., 2023). These measures are critical in preparing for and effectively managing future public health emergencies.

Management of crisis

Crisis management involves timely and coordinated policies and actions implemented by governments to effectively respond to and address crises (OECD 2022). This encompasses crisis communication, government arrangements, and a whole-of-society response.

Crisis communication

Transparent communication with the public during the COVID-19 pandemic fostered trust and compliance with containment measures (Thomas et al., 2020). Countries such as Singapore, Trinidad, Tobago, and Vietnam utilized regular media briefings and transparent information sharing through official and social media (Chua et al., 2020; Ha et al., 2020; Hunte et al., 2020). Ecuador provided reliable information and practical hygiene measures, (Alava & Guevara, 2021) whereas New York's local health departments used various channels and trusted messengers to reach underserved communities and boost vaccination rates (Bloomstone et al., 2022).

Community engagement proved crucial for enhancing disease control and promoting health literacy during the pandemic, facilitating collaboration and adaptability in response strategies. The Eastern Mediterranean region emphasized active community engagement and transparent communication to promote public health measures and acceptance of COVID-19 vaccination (Abubakar *et al.*, 2021). Oman used community participation through organizations, health committees, and volunteers, while Cambodia's Ministry of Health implemented risk communication and engagement campaigns (Al Siyabi et al., 2021; Chhim et al., 2023). African countries like Rwanda, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Nigeria, and Malawi utilized diverse channels,

including SMS, WhatsApp, radio, television, and hotlines, to disseminate verified information, debunk rumors, and raise awareness about COVID-19 (Akande et al., 2023; Dzinamarira et al., 2020; Mghamba et al., 2023; Moonasar et al., 2021; Okeke et al., 2022; Talisuna et al., 2022). Community-based programs and capacity-building initiatives strengthened responses in Congo and Uganda (Corbin et al., 2021; Thu et al., 2022). CHWs in South Africa and Tanzania play a vital role in bridging communities and health systems, emphasizing community buy-in and addressing the social determinants of health (Gebremeskel *et al.*, 2021).

Governance arrangements

Countries adopted various governance approaches during the pandemic, each with distinct outcomes. Germany's decentralized approach empowered regional authorities, while Austria and Switzerland relied on centralized decision-making and effectively managed the health crisis. France's centralized approach facilitated resource coordination but caused delays in testing policies. Canada's decentralized setting resulted in varying success rates, and Belgium faced challenges due to the shared responsibilities between national and regional governments. Federated countries such as the US, Spain, and Australia witnessed governance variations, with states taking the lead. In Southeast Asia, responses were marked by controversies, power asymmetries, and political instability (Desson, Lambertz, et al., 2020; Desson, Weller, et al., 2020; Djalante et al., 2020; Ha et al., 2020; Kavanagh et al., 2021).

Strong high-level political leadership was crucial in coordinating stakeholders and strengthening health systems (Thomas *et al.*, 2020). Ethiopia, Trinidad, and Tobago demonstrated strong leadership through coordination structures, such as the PHEOC and the COVID Plan (Hunte *et al.*, 2020; Lanyero *et al.*, 2021). Countries utilized multi-ministerial coordination platforms, such as task forces and committees, for a whole-of-nation response. Ethiopia, Singapore, Iran, Guyana, and Sri Lanka implemented such approaches (Chua *et al.*, 2020; Gouya *et al.*, 2023; Mghamba *et al.*, 2023). Coordinated responses, including regional collaborations such as the Africa CDC and the European Union's joint vaccine procurement, were crucial (Beesley et al., 2023; Lanyero et al., 2021). Effective governance involved transparency, accountability, and informed decision-making. Denmark, Switzerland, Italy, and Ethiopia exemplified these practices (Lanyero et al., 2021; Tille et al., 2022). Collaborative leadership and stakeholder involvement fostered trust (Assefa, Woldeyohannes, et al., 2022; Bigoni et al., 2022; Burke et al., 2021; Tille et al., 2022; Thu et al., 2022). Flexibility in decision-making, and addressing challenges such as misinformation was crucial. (Djalante et al., 2020; Forsgren et al., 2022)

Whole-of-society response

Whole-of-society response involved stakeholder engagement and partnerships among government agencies, communities, NGOs, and CSOs to collectively implement preventive measures, and mobilize and manage resources to minimize the pandemic impact (Aisyah et al., 2022). Several strategies emerged from the analysis of this area. Rwanda, South Africa, Zimbabwe, and Nigeria successfully engaged stakeholders from various sectors in their COVID-19 response (Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2021; Okeke *et al.*, 2022). In Ethiopia, private partnerships expanded emergency response capacity through collaboration with university institutions, private hospitals, and laboratories (Lanyero *et al.*, 2021). Strategic partnerships with international agencies and organizations enhanced COVID-19 response and management, such as the collaboration between the Pasteur Institute of Dakar and a UK-based biotech laboratory, leading to a rapid diagnostic test in Ethiopia

(Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2020). Community engagement through partnerships with local leaders and CHWs played a pivotal role in supporting non-pharmaceutical interventions, maintaining essential health services, and providing medication in countries such as Thailand, Singapore, Liberia, and the US (Haldane *et al.*, 2021; Bloomstone *et al.*, 2022).

Response and recovery

The response and recovery policies aimed at mitigating the impacts of the pandemic and economic crisis on citizens and businesses, supporting economic recovery, and reducing welfare losses (OECD 2022). These policies encompassed lockdown and restriction measures, economic and financial support, social policies, and health measures.

Lockdown and restrictions

Many countries implemented various travel restrictions and bans. Germany, Australia, and Singapore enforced strict measures such as cruise line bans, quarantine requirements, and limited overseas travel (Kavanagh *et al.*, 2021). Bulgaria, Croatia, and Romania initially imposed border closures, flight suspensions, and educational institution closures, which led to societal and economic consequences (Džakula *et al.*, 2022). Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania implemented early and effective lockdown measures, clear communication, and strengthened testing and contact tracing efforts (Webb, Winkelmann *et al.*, 2022). Asian countries such as China, Singapore, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and South Korea successfully flattened their curves through lockdowns, testing, and rapid responses (Khanna *et al.*, 2020; Tabish, 2020). Some European and American countries faced challenges owing to delayed containment measures, leading to devastating surges and lockdowns (Desson, Weller, *et al.*, 2020; Khanna *et al.*, 2020).

In Africa, most countries responded swiftly to strict lockdowns, providing PPE, testing, and isolating infected individuals (Talisuna *et al.*, 2022; Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2020, 2021; Emahi *et al.*, 2021). Rwanda and Uganda demonstrated exemplary responses by prioritizing social distancing and travel restrictions even before registering their first cases (Binagwaho *et al.*, 2020).

Countries also implemented strategies to scale up contact tracing during the COVID-19 pandemic, redirecting health workers, digitalizing tracing operations, and contracting with outsourcing corporations. Germany allocated €50 million to digitalization and hiring tracers, while Austria's local health offices led contact tracing. Inadequate support for isolating individuals, especially those with low incomes or precarious jobs, led to continued normal activities (Tille *et al.*, 2022).

Port of entries (PoEs)

Countries implemented various strategic responses to enhance preparedness at PoE in managing the COVID-19 pandemic, including enhanced health screening, information gathering, and contact tracing for arriving passengers. African countries adhered to WHO International Health Regulations (IHR) with measures such as mandatory negative COVID-19 PCR tests for travelers. Rwanda implemented repeat testing and 24-hour quarantine, whereas South Africa and Zimbabwe conducted pre-arrival testing. Stricter measures addressed the challenges of fake certificates (Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2020, 2021). Ethiopian Airlines played a crucial role in training staff and transporting medical supplies (Lanyero *et al.*, 2021). Taiwan and Hong Kong employed passenger screening, flight suspensions, and mandatory quarantine for travelers from

Wuhan(Tabish, 2020). Singapore, Israel, and South Korea used mobile apps for contact tracing and enforced various travel restrictions(Chua et al., 2020; Kuguyo et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021). Ecuador closed its borders to exposed countries and established testing and tracing capacities(Alava & Guevara, 2021). International collaboration addressed cross-border economic challenges (Binagwaho et al., 2022)

Economic and financial support

COVID-19 required sustained funding for outbreak response, and countries employed various strategies. Health financing policies were crucial in resource-constrained settings, with competing priorities(Bhatia & Abraham, 2022). Public funds were used for testing, treatment, vaccines, and supporting businesses and low-income households (Haldane et al., 2021). Countries tapped into reserves, reallocated budgets, and borrowed funds to manage increased health expenditure and economic impact(Sagan et al., 2022). In Europe, Germany, Austria, Switzerland, France, and Belgium introduced substantial support packages, with Germany allocating €156 billion to the MOH (Desson, Lambertz, *et al.*, 2020; Desson, Weller, *et al.*, 2020). Spain and Ireland utilized private-sector capacity (Thomas *et al.*, 2020).

Canada implemented wage subsidies and financial aid (Alami et al., 2021; Desson, Weller, et al., 2020). Singapore committed 60 billion SGD in Asia to support businesses and livelihoods, and Thailand implemented stimulus packages totaling 217 billion baht (Chua *et al.*, 2020; Djalante *et al.*, 2020). In Africa, Morocco, Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Mauritania, and Sudan implemented various measures, including a USD 3.3 billion COVID-19 Fund in Morocco and an IMF Rapid Credit Facility disbursement of \$130 million in Mauritania (Elbeshbishi et al., 2020; Fakher & Abiari, 2020). Nigeria mobilized funds from the 2020 budget and special intervention funds, while South Africa allocated \$10.6 million for aid and relief (Adebisi et al., 2021; Okeke et al., 2022; United Nations, 2021). Addressing corruption within governments was crucial, with Rwanda's anti-corruption model serving as an exemplar (Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2021). Flexibility in payment systems and incentivizing telemedicine were also observed (Sagan *et al.*, 2022; Thomas *et al.*, 2020)

Social policies

The analysis identified several social protection measures implemented by various countries to address social disparities and mitigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. African countries introduced several social protection measures, primarily focusing on non-contributory programs such as special allowances, food, nutrition protection, and health support. However, aspects such as access to education, sickness benefits, and family benefits received less attention. Women's needs were also overlooked, with only 16% of interventions specifically targeting them (United Nations, 2021). Access to essential services such as water and sanitation posed challenges, hindering viral control, especially in vulnerable communities in South Africa and Zimbabwe(Banda Chitsamatanga & Malinga, 2021). European countries provided extensive job and enterprise protection, coupled with solidaristic policies to care for the most vulnerable, including strengthened minimum income schemes, but access remained challenging for non-standard workers. (Baptista et al., 2021). Arab countries used digital delivery methods for social protection targeting informal workers, foreign workers, persons with disabilities, and refugees (Iyer *et al.*, 2021). Canada and the US addressed housing, employment, and social assistance challenges with various measures(Béland et al., 2021). Several countries enhanced their health services to make them accessible to all, including non-nationals in Trinidad and Tobago, Estonia, Latvia, and

Lithuania(Hunte et al., 2020; Webb, Winkelmann, et al., 2022). Singapore's private insurers extended coverage for COVID-19 hospitalization, but noncompliance with travel advisories resulted in ineligible subsidies at public hospitals (Chua *et al.*, 2020).

Health measures

Health measures encompass human resource strategies, maintenance of essential services, case management, facility-based infection prevention and control (IPC), logistics and operational support, laboratory diagnosis and management, and vaccine management.

Human resource

The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated health workforce shortages in many countries, leading to the adoption of various HR response strategies to address the surge in demand, protect healthcare workers, and scale-up capacity(Assefa, Gilks, et al., 2022; Džakula et al., 2022; Fleming et al., 2022; Haldane et al., 2021; Hunte et al., 2020; Williams, Maier, et al., 2022; Williams, Scarpetti, et al., 2022).

Several countries, including Germany, Russia, Spain, the UK, Vietnam, the Netherlands, Austria, Portugal, and Trinidad and Tobago, increased recruitment quotas and enlisted medical and nursing students using emergency legislation (Assefa *et al.*, 2022a; Burau *et al.*, 2022; Džakula *et al.*, 2020; Haldane *et al.*, 2021; Hunte *et al.*, 2020; Williams, Maier, *et al.*, 2022, Williams, Scarpetti, *et al.*, 2022). International collaborations facilitated the deployment of health professionals in regions with high COVID-19 cases (Williams, Maier, *et al.*, 2022). Countries have simplified registration and hiring processes to include foreign-trained health professionals in their workforce. England extended visas for frontline workers from abroad, and France mobilized a "medical care reserve" consisting of various health professionals (Winkelmann, Panteli, et al., 2022) Iran utilized military staff, volunteers, and post-graduate students to support frontline healthcare providers (Gouya *et al.*, 2023). Canadian Armed Forces and Canadian Red Cross reinforced CHSLDs (Alami *et al.*, 2021).

Scaling up capacity involved extending work hours, modifying schedules, and redeploying primary care workers in emergency care wards and ICUs in countries like Croatia, Estonia, Lithuania, Malta, the Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Italy, and Spain (Haldane *et al.*, 2021; Tille *et al.*, 2022; Williams, Maier, *et al.*, 2022). Skill mix changes allowed various professionals to administer vaccinations, and non-health personnel were engaged to support the non-clinical aspects of testing and vaccination programs(Buchan et al., 2021; Williams, Maier, et al., 2022). Canada authorized private-sector physicians to practice in the public sector alongside their private practice and engaged private clinics and physicians to address procedure delays caused by COVID-19(Alami et al., 2021). Protecting health workers involved implementing hygiene protocols, providing sufficient PPEs, and offering remote consultation. Vaccination, infection control policies, and regular testing were also prioritized to safeguard healthcare workers (Chua *et al.*, 2020; Džakula *et al.*, 2020; Haldane *et al.*, 2021; Hunte *et al.*, 2020; Tille *et al.*, 2022; Williams, Scarpetti, *et al.*, 2022)

Maintaining essential health service delivery

Countries adopted diverse approaches to sustain essential healthcare amid COVID-19. For instance, Slovenia made a task shift from GPs to nurses to reduce the GP workload in primary care

(Thomas *et al.*, 2020). Sri Lanka ensured routine care for non-communicable diseases while managing COVID-19 through a whole-of-society approach (Mghamba *et al.*, 2023). In some countries, the private sector was utilized to maintain essential health services. To mitigate disruptions in service delivery, triaging and alternative care models such as home-based care and telemedicine were adopted. Care pathways were adjusted within hospital facilities to segregate COVID-19 patients and ensure safe treatment. Telehealth and digital consultations were widely adopted to maintain essential care and minimize exposure risks (Assaye & Shimie, 2022; Assefa, Gilks, et al., 2022; Webb, Lenormand, *et al.*, 2022; Williams, Fahy, *et al.*, 2022). The pandemic emphasized the need to strengthen long-term resilience and capacity in the health sector, particularly in primary care and public health (Alami *et al.*, 2021).

Case management

Prompt deployment of experts and guidelines to guide the clinical management of COVID-19 cases was observed in most countries (Talisuna *et al.*, 2022; Okeke *et al.*, 2022). Vietnam established a center for managing clinical support for COVID-19 patients, while Trinidad and Tobago increased their healthcare capacity by screening and isolating suspected cases (Ha *et al.*, 2020; Hunte *et al.*, 2020). Some countries adopted home-based and community case management models to reduce pressure on the health system, but challenges arose due to the lack of specialized hospitals and technical expertise for severe cases. Shortages of critical supplies strained case management, prompting countries like South Sudan and Ethiopia to establish specialized treatment facilities (Talisuna *et al.*, 2022; Olu *et al.*, 2022; Lanyero *et al.*, 2021). Countries managed acute care and ICU capacity by postponing elective treatments, designating specific hospitals, and utilizing private ICUs and field hospitals, while hospital networks and cross-border cooperation were crucial for effective management (Khanna *et al.*, 2020; Winkelmann, Panteli *et al.*, 2022; Winkelmann, Webb, *et al.*, 2022).

Facility-based IPC

Facility-based IPC measures were critical in managing the spread of COVID-19. The analysis identified several strategies implemented by various countries in this area. In Singapore, strict IPC measures were enforced, including temperature checks, mandatory PPE usage, and visitor controls. Innovative solutions like the 'SG SAFE' booth were implemented for large-scale screening (Chua *et al.*, 2020). African countries focused on capacity building, guidelines, and environmental controls to reduce the spread of COVID-19 (Balde *et al.*, 2022; Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2021; Olu *et al.*, 2022). Some countries faced challenges with poor adherence and enforcement of IPC measures, leading to shortages of PPEs and irrational use. Additionally, inadequate water supply in health facilities compromised IPC measures, and the indiscriminate disposal of surgical masks was observed. (Abu & Elliott, 2022; Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2021; Talisuna *et al.*, 2022)

Operational support and logistics

Globally, countries employed diverse strategies to boost healthcare capacity during the COVID-19 pandemic. Some nations (Ireland, England, Italy, North Macedonia, Spain, and Russia) block-booked private hospitals, while others (Switzerland and Italy) enacted emergency legislation to acquire private facilities. Some countries also established field hospitals. Innovative procurement and international collaborations addressed equipment shortages (Khanna *et al.*, 2020; Winkelmann, Webb *et al.*, 2022). Japan, the UK, the US, South Korea, and Ecuador employed various approaches, including resource distribution and domestic production encouragement. Europe

utilized digital tools for telemedicine, streamlined administrative procedures, and real-time monitoring through digital registries and dashboards (Džakula *et al.*, 2020; Winkelmann, Webb, *et al.*, 2022; Winkelmann, Panteli, *et al.*, 2022).

Several EU countries planned investments in digital infrastructure, (Bhaskar *et al.*, 2021; Van Ginneken *et al.*, 2022; Webb, Winkelmann, *et al.*, 2022; Williams, Fahy, *et al.*, 2022;) and in the Asia-Pacific region, Taiwan regulated mask distribution and encouraged domestic production. Singapore's National Center for Infectious Diseases coordinated outbreak management (Chang *et al.*, 2020; Chua *et al.*, 2020). African nations effectively utilized digital solutions; Uganda leveraged eELMIS to track and distribute COVID-19 supplies; and Rwanda used a national command post for surveillance and contact tracing. Ethiopia and South Sudan utilized global platforms for procurement, and Nigeria improved its healthcare infrastructure (Lanyero *et al.*, 2021; Mghamba *et al.*, 2023; Moonasar *et al.*, 2021; Okeke *et al.*, 2022; Wasswa *et al.*, 2023). Trinidad and Tobago collaborated with regional partners for procurement and relied on local manufacturers for supplies (Hunte *et al.*, 2020).

Laboratory diagnosis and management

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the critical importance of rapid and accurate laboratory diagnostic testing in various countries. The analysis identified various strategies implemented by countries in this area. Indonesia established 685 referral laboratories for COVID-19 testing, despite facing challenges with staff, reagent supply, and PPE shortages. South Korea's large-scale testing program tested over 270,000 people (Aisyah *et al.*, 2022; Tabish, 2020). In Europe, Germany used robust laboratory infrastructure to expand its testing. Denmark adapted its testing strategy over time, including milder symptoms and asymptomatic individuals. Smaller European nations utilized repurposed labs and sent samples abroad. Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania established separate testing locations and flexible mobile sites (Tille *et al.*, 2022; Webb, Winkelmann, *et al.*, 2022). In the WHO African region, early testing faced challenges due to reagent shortages. However, progress was made with rapid antigen tests and the COVID-19 sequencing laboratory network. Community-based surveillance using Ag-RDT reached over 7 million people. African countries such as Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, and Ethiopia expanded testing centers through collaborations with the private sector, repurposing research facilities, and establishing networks of existing labs (Balde *et al.*, 2022; Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2021; Lanyero *et al.*, 2021; Okeke *et al.*, 2022; Talisuna *et al.*, 2022; Tessema *et al.*, 2021).

Vaccine management

Several countries, including Singapore and China, implemented effective COVID-19 vaccination plans through policy measures and transparent communication to build public trust (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Iran utilized its primary healthcare supply chain and mass vaccination centers, achieving a primary vaccination coverage rate of approximately 75% by January 2022. They developed local production capacity for domestic COVID-19 vaccines with WHO support (Gouya *et al.*, 2023). Ecuador, the Central African Republic, and New York, USA, efficiently distributed vaccines through task shifting, community engagement, and partnerships with stakeholders. Digital health tools played a vital role in successful vaccine rollout (Alava & Guevara, 2021; Amani *et al.*, 2023; Bloomstone *et al.*, 2022; Williams, Fahy, *et al.*, 2022). South Sudan utilized existing immunization systems for COVID-19 vaccination, straining health workers (Olu *et al.*, 2022).

Discussion

Ghana's COVID-19 response saw successes. However, there were challenges such as sporadic PPE shortages, geographical limitations in testing for COVID-19, delayed test deliveries, understaffed treatment centers, and insufficient COVID-19 lab supplies. Other concerns included safety protocol adherence, equipment readiness, healthcare infrastructure, funding, human resources, transparent vaccine procurement, and equitable healthcare (Ayee, 2022; Sarkodie *et al.*, 2021). These challenges encountered during the pandemic have ignited a growing interest in strengthening Ghana's healthcare system resilience. However, a dearth of comprehensive studies that synthesize global experiences and provide evidence-based insights for fortifying the nation's health system resilience persists. Thus, despite Ghana's commendable handling of the pandemic, learning from worldwide experience can further enhance its readiness for future emergencies. This review extracted pandemic-derived strategies to guide Ghana in building its health system resilience

From our review, ten critical response strategies emerged, where Ghana can draw valuable lessons to enhance its preparedness for future health emergencies. These strategies align closely with Kruk *et al.*'s (2017) five core attributes of health system resilience, which include system awareness, integration, self-regulation, diversity, and adaptability.

Whole-of-government engagement

The findings of this study suggest that decisive and committed political leadership, demonstrated in various countries (Hunte *et al.*, 2020; Lanyero *et al.*, 2021; Thomas *et al.*, 2020; Haldane *et al.*, 2021), is crucial for effective responses to health crises. This corresponds to the system awareness attribute, which underscores the importance of tracking health and mapping resources for effective response. Additionally, engaging multiple sectors beyond the health sector through whole-of-government efforts (Chua *et al.*, 2020; Gouya *et al.*, 2023; Mghamba *et al.*, 2023) demonstrates integration, highlighting the need for coordinated efforts and societal engagement. Embracing pluralistic and adaptive leadership supported by an expanded governance framework (Alami *et al.*, 2021; Assefa, Woldeyohannes, *et al.*, 2022; Lanyero *et al.*, 2021; Tille *et al.*, 2022; Thu *et al.*, 2022) also aligns with the adaptability attribute. It demonstrates the importance of flexible responses and evidence-based decision-making in different situations. Ghana can draw from these strategies to build a resilient health system, address the social determinants of health, and prepare for future health emergencies.

Financing for preparedness

The sustained funding strategies adopted by countries during the COVID-19 response highlight the critical role of health financing policies, especially in resource-constrained settings with competing priorities (Bhatia & Abraham, 2022). These efforts align with the self-regulation and adaptability attributes of health system resilience. Self-regulation was evident in the reallocation of budgets, tapping into reserves, and borrowing funds to manage increased health expenditure and economic impact. Adaptability was demonstrated by countries like Germany, Austria, Switzerland, France, and Belgium (Desson, Lambertz, *et al.*, 2020; Desson, Weller, *et al.*, 2020) introducing substantial support packages. This underscores the flexibility needed to address unforeseen challenges. Ghana can learn from these strategies to strengthen the financial capacity

of its health system. This will allow it to self-regulate and adapt swiftly to changing circumstances, ultimately enhancing its ability to withstand and effectively manage health crises.

Robust surveillance system

The findings of this study underscore the importance of a robust surveillance system in enhancing health system and societal resilience. Effective surveillance systems, as seen in South Korea, Vietnam, Singapore, China, and Australia (Chua *et al.*, 2020; Sundararaman *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2021; Williams, Fahy, *et al.*, 2022) enabled timely containment measures. This reflects the significance of system awareness and integration attributes of health system resilience. The enhanced disease detection in Congo, Nigeria, Senegal, and Uganda through diverse surveillance approaches during the pandemic as noted in this study (Okeke *et al.*, 2022; Fawole *et al.*, 2023) underscores the critical role of diversity in fostering health system resilience. Integrating digital health tools like Big Data and Nigeria's SORMAS enhances monitoring (Chang *et al.*, 2020; Kuguyo *et al.*, 2020; Mghamba *et al.*, 2023; Okeke *et al.*, 2022). The use of various tools such as GPS tracking, credit card records, surveillance videos, and mobile apps to enhance their surveillance system (Wang *et al.*, 2021) aligns with adaptation attributes of the health system's resilience. By incorporating these lessons, Ghana can reinforce its health system resilience against future health emergencies.

Emergency medical care

The diverse strategies employed in emergency care during the pandemic, as noted in this study, provide valuable lessons for Ghana's health system resilience. Involving the private sector and alternative care models can enhance emergency capacity (Assefa, Gilks, *et al.*, 2022; Thomas *et al.*, 2020; Webb *et al.*, 2022). This reflects diversity and integration in health system resilience. Effective case management, timely expert deployment, and cross-border collaboration for acute care and ICU surge capacity are crucial components in emergency preparedness, as highlighted by various studies (Khanna *et al.*, 2020; Olu *et al.*, 2022; Talisuna *et al.*, 2022; Winkelmann, Panteli *et al.*, 2022; Winkelmann, Webb, *et al.*, 2022). These strategies align with system awareness and adaptation attributes of health system resilience. Again, improving laboratory testing capabilities, decentralizing testing through regional networks, and reinforcing infection prevention measures (Abu & Elliott 2022; Balde *et al.*, 2022; Chua *et al.*, 2020; Dzinamarira *et al.*, 2021; Lanyero *et al.*, 2021; Okeke *et al.*, 2022; Talisuna *et al.*, 2022; Tessema *et al.*, 2021; Tille *et al.*, 2022; Webb, Winkelmann *et al.*, 2022) are crucial for system awareness, self-regulation, and adaptation. Ghana can strengthen its emergency medical care and health system resilience by applying these lessons.

Community engagement and trust

The vital role of community engagement and trust during the COVID-19 pandemic is underlined by the findings of this study. Involving communities and promoting transparent communication fosters collaboration and strengthens response adaptability and legitimacy (Al Siyabi *et al.*, 2021; Chhim *et al.*, 2023; Corbin *et al.*, 2021; Thu *et al.*, 2022). For future pandemics, Ghana should prioritize community involvement, leveraging trusted local messengers for risk communication. This approach fosters integration, strengthens adaptability, and ensures systems awareness, self-regulation, diversity, and legitimacy in responses, which are integral to a resilient health system.

Diverse workforce development

The COVID-19 pandemic, as noted in this review, intensified health workforce shortages globally, prompting the adoption of diverse human resources strategies to cope with increased demand and protect healthcare workers (Assefa, Gilks, *et al.*, 2022; Džakula *et al.*, 2022; Fleming *et al.*, 2022; Haldane *et al.*, 2021; Hunte *et al.*, 2020; Williams, Maier, *et al.*, 2022; Williams, Scarpetti, *et al.*, 2022). Implementing emergency legislation by several countries to increase recruitment quotas and changing schedules, redeploying workers, and engaging a diverse workforce to scale up capacity demonstrated adaptability and integration while international collaborations and simplified registration processes showcased system awareness and diversity. Protection measures, including hygiene protocols and adequate PPE, illustrated self-regulation. To enhance its health system resilience, Ghana can learn from these lessons by strategically addressing workforce shortages, fostering international collaborations, adapting to changing demands, and prioritizing the well-being and protection of its healthcare workers.

Digital health integration

This review underscores the importance of digital health solutions in the pandemic response. Leveraging digital health technology such as big data, telemedicine, GPS tracking, credit card records, surveillance videos, mobile applications, syndromic surveillance, eELMIS for supply tracking, and SORMAS for real-time monitoring, were evident in managing COVID-19 impact and strengthening healthcare systems (Chang *et al.*, 2020; Haldane *et al.*, 2021; Kuguyo *et al.*, 2020; Lanyero *et al.*, 2021; Mghamba *et al.*, 2023; Moonasar *et al.*, 2021; Okeke *et al.*, 2022; Wasswa *et al.*, 2023; Williams, Fahy, *et al.*, 2022). Using digital tools for standardized detection and response enhances system awareness, expanding access demonstrates diversity, and the integration of digital solutions with healthcare practices underscores integration. Ghana should prioritize investment in digital health solutions, expand access to underserved areas, and ensure robust training, supportive policies, and regulatory frameworks to enhance its preparedness to cope with future emergencies.

Critical health infrastructure

The need to enhance healthcare infrastructure, particularly maintaining critical ICU devices in strategic reserves for rapid response, outfitting emergency units, establishing robust laboratory networks to expand testing centers, establishing well-equipped infectious treatment centers, and oxygen and therapeutics production and delivery, emerged as a critical factor for future public health emergency preparedness and management (Gebremeskel *et al.*, 2021; Gouya *et al.*, 2023). A resilient health system entails diverse and well-equipped healthcare facilities. Continuous investment and improvement in critical healthcare infrastructure can enhance adaptability and allow the health system to transform its operations, respond flexibly to various situations, and strengthen its overall ability to withstand and manage health crises. Ghana can draw lessons from global insights to prioritize critical health infrastructure investments. Engaging the private sector through public-private partnerships can be beneficial in critical health infrastructure investment, but effective regulatory capacity is essential to ensure successful collaborations (Gebremeskel *et al.*, 2021).

Well-planned commodities/products

Innovative procurement and international collaborations were crucial in addressing shortages of equipment, logistics, and vaccines during the COVID-19 response (Khanna *et al.*, 2020; Winkelmann, Webb *et al.*, 2022). Countries implemented diverse strategies, including resource distribution and encouragement of domestic production. Iran's development of local production capacity for domestic COVID-19 vaccines with WHO support and their accomplishment of a 75% primary vaccination coverage (Gouya *et al.*, 2023) demonstrated adaptability and self-regulation. Drawing lessons from these successful strategies, Ghana should vigorously pursue its aspiration to develop local pharmaceutical and vaccine production capacity. This will strengthen the country's medical supplies capacity, enhance self-reliance, and support global health security.

Social capital

Social protection responses to the COVID-19 pandemic varied widely across the globe. African nations focused on non-contributory programs such as special allowances, food, nutrition protection, and health support, but gaps persisted in education and gender-specific interventions (United Nations, 2021). Some African countries also faced challenges in accessing essential services, particularly water and sanitation, hindering effective viral control in vulnerable communities. Ghana can strengthen the resilience of its health system against future emergencies by adopting a diverse range of social protection schemes with sustainable financing. Prioritizing crisis-related needs, incorporating a gender perspective, and tailoring support for vulnerable groups is essential for strengthening social protection (Iyer *et al.*, 2021; United Nations, 2021;). Again, Ghana should focus more attention on enhancing access to water, sanitation, and healthcare, particularly in vulnerable communities.

Limitations

This review is not without limitations. The review examined an extensive range of studies and grey literature. Although beneficial, exploring a wide array of studies in this review posed a challenge in synthesizing findings across various methodologies within the study framework. Besides, the study's reliance solely on existing literature could restrict its ability to fully capture countries' specific context. This could potentially limit the lessons that could be drawn to enhance Ghana's health system resilience against future emergencies. Furthermore, the study's exclusive focus on the COVID-19 pandemic might neglect other factors impacting Ghana's readiness for future emergencies. Future research could broaden its focus beyond COVID-19 to include other health emergencies or crises. This will allow a more comprehensive analysis of Ghana's resilience across various contexts. Despite the constraints highlighted above, the review offers valuable insights for informing health system resilience strategies in Ghana.

Conclusions

Ghana's response to the COVID-19 pandemic revealed challenges despite some successes. This underscores the need to enhance the country's healthcare system resilience against future health emergencies. This study extracts valuable lessons from global experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic to guide Ghana's future health emergency preparedness. The findings of this study

emphasize the critical role of whole-of-government engagement, financing for preparedness, community engagement and trust, robust surveillance systems, emergency medical care, diverse workforce development, digital health integration, critical health infrastructure, well-planned commodities/products, and social capital in fostering a resilient health system. These essential areas of response align with the attributes of a resilient healthcare system such as awareness, integration, self-regulation, diversity, and adaptability. By adopting these strategies, Ghana can build a resilient healthcare system that effectively addresses future challenges, guided by global insights and experiences.

Data availability

All underlying data are available as part of the article and no additional source data are required.

Extended data

Repository name: Extended data for ‘Building resilience of the Ghanaian healthcare system: Lessons from a global health stage: Preparedness for the next pandemic: Scoping Review’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11154359> (Ankomah *et al.*, 2023)

This project contains the following extended data:

Reporting guidelines

Repository name: PRISMA-ScR checklist for ‘Building resilience of the Ghanaian healthcare system: Lessons from a global health stage: Preparedness for the next pandemic: Scoping Review’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11154359> (Ankomah *et al.*, 2023)

License: **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**

Competing interests

No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information

The authors declared that no grants were involved in supporting this work.

References

- Abu, T. Z., & Elliott, S. J. (2022). The critical need for WASH in emergency preparedness in health settings, the case of COVID-19 pandemic in Kisumu Kenya. *Health and Place*, 76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2022.102841>
- Abubakar, A., Khan, W., Abou El Naja, H., Al Ariqi, L., Bélorgeot, V. D., & Hauck, S. J. (2022). COVID-19 pandemic response in the WHO Eastern Mediterranean Region. *BMJ Global Health*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2022-008782>
- Adebisi, Y. A., Ekpenyong, A., Ntacyabukura, B., Lowe, M., Jimoh, N. D., Abdulkareem, T. O., & Lucero-Prisno, D. E. (2021). COVID-19 highlights the need for inclusive responses to public health emergencies in Africa. In *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* (Vol. 104, Issue 2, pp. 449–452). American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.20-1485>
- Aidukaite, J., Saxonberg, S., Szelewa, D., & Szikra, D. (2021). Social policy in the face of a global pandemic: Policy responses to the COVID-19 crisis in Central and Eastern Europe. *Social Policy and Administration*, 55(2), 358–373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spol.12704>
- Aisyah, D. N., Mayadewi, C. A., Budiharsana, M., Solikha, D. A., Ali, P. B., Igusti, G., Kozlakidis, Z., & Manikam, L. (2022). Building on health security capacities in Indonesia: Lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic responses and challenges. *Zoonoses and Public Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12976>
- Akande, O. W., Disu, Y., Kaduru, C., Anueyiagu, C., Oguanuo, E., Ojumu, T., Akomolafe, O., Eziechina, S. O., Ejibe, U., Ihekweazu, V., Ochu, C. L., & Ihekweazu, C. (2023). Risk communication during health emergencies in Nigeria: What are its challenges? *Journal of Public Health in Africa*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.4081/jphia.2023.1943>
- Al Siyabi, H., Al Mukhaini, S., Kanaan, M., Al Hatmi, S., Al Anqoudi, Z., Al Kalbani, A., Al Bahri, Z., Wannous, C., & Al Awaidy, S. T. (2021). Community Participation Approaches for Effective National COVID-19 Pandemic Preparedness and Response: An Experience From Oman. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.616763>
- Alami, H., Lehoux, P., Fleet, R., Fortin, J. P., Liu, J., Attieh, R., Cadeddu, S. B. M., Abdoulaye Samri, M., Savoldelli, M., & Ag Ahmed, M. A. (2021). How Can Health Systems Better Prepare for the Next Pandemic? Lessons Learned From the Management of COVID-19 in Quebec (Canada). In *Frontiers in public health* (Vol. 9, p. 671833). NLM (Medline). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.671833>
- Alava, J. J., & Guevara, A. (2021). A critical narrative of Ecuador's preparedness and response to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Public Health in Practice*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhip.2021.100127>
- Amani, A., Atuhebwe, P., Mboussou, F. F., Ngoy, N., M'boufoungou, N. E., Osei-Sarpong, F., Traore, C., Mihigo, R., & Chaiban, T. (2023). A rapid increase in coverage of COVID-19 vaccination, Central African Republic. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 101(6), 431–436. <https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.22.289155>
- Amin Tabish, S. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic: Emerging perspectives and future trends. In *Journal of Public Health Research* (Vol. 9).

- Ankomah, M. Patience Aseweh Abor, P.A., Karamagi, H. (2024). Extended data for ‘Building resilience of the Ghanaian healthcare system: Lessons from a global health stage: Preparedness for the next pandemic: Scoping Review’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11107062>
- Ankomah, M. Patience Aseweh Abor, P.A., Karamagi, H. (2024). PRISMA-ScR checklist for ‘Building resilience of the Ghanaian healthcare system: Lessons from a global health stage: Preparedness for the next pandemic: Scoping Review’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11107062>
- Arabi, Y. M., Azoulay, E., Al-Dorzi, H. M., Phua, J., Salluh, J., Binnie, A., Hodgson, C., Angus, D. C., Cecconi, M., Du, B., Fowler, R., Gomersall, C. D., Horby, P., Juffermans, N. P., Kesecioglu, J., Kleinpell, R. M., Machado, F. R., Martin, G. S., Meyfroidt, G., ... Citerio, G. (2021). How the COVID-19 pandemic will change the future of critical care. In *Intensive Care Medicine* (Vol. 47, Issue 3, pp. 282–291). Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-021-06352-y>
- Assaye, B. T., & Shimie, A. worku. (2022). Telemedicine use during COVID-19 pandemics and associated factors among health professionals working in health facilities at resource-limited setting 2021. *Informatics in Medicine Unlocked*, 33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2022.101085>
- Assefa, Y., Gilks, C. F., Reid, S., van de Pas, R., Gete, D. G., & Van Damme, W. (2022). Analysis of the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons towards a more effective response to public health emergencies. *Globalization and Health*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-022-00805-9>
- Assefa, Y., Woldeyohannes, S., Cullerton, K., Gilks, C. F., Reid, S., & Van Damme, W. (2022). Attributes of national governance for an effective response to public health emergencies: Lessons from the response to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Global Health*, 12, 05021. <https://doi.org/10.7189/jogh.12.05021>
- Balde, T., Oyugi, B., Byakika-Tusiime, J., Ogundiran, O., Kayita, J., Banza, F. M., Landry, K., Ejiofor, E. N., Kanyowa, T. M., Mbasha, J.-J., Rashidatu, K., Atuhebwe, P., Gumede, N., Herring, B. L., Anoko, J. N., Zongo, M., Okeibunor, J., O’Malley, H., Chamla, D., ... Gueye, A. S. (2022). Transitioning the COVID-19 response in the WHO African region: a proposed framework for rethinking and rebuilding health systems. *BMJ Global Health*, 7(12). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2022-010242>
- Banda Chitsamatanga, B., & Malinga, W. (2021). ‘A tale of two paradoxes in response to COVID-19’: Public health system and socio-economic implications of the pandemic in South Africa and Zimbabwe. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2020.1869368>
- Baptista, I., Marlier, E., Spasova, S., Peña-Casas, R., Fronteddu, B., Ghailani, D., Sabato, S., & Regazzoni, P. (n.d.). *Title Authors Social protection and inclusion policy responses to the COVID-19 crisis An analysis of policies in 35 countries*.
- Beesley, L. J., Patelli, P., Kaufeld, K., Schwenk, J., Martinez, K. M., Pitts, T., Barnard, M., McMahon, B., & Del Valle, S. Y. (2023). Multi-dimensional resilience: A quantitative exploration of disease outcomes and economic, political, and social resilience to the COVID-19 pandemic in six countries. *PLoS ONE*, 18(1 January). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0279894>

- Béland, D., Dinan, S., Rocco, P., & Waddan, A. (2021). Social policy responses to COVID-19 in Canada and the United States: Explaining policy variations between two liberal welfare state regimes. *Social Policy and Administration*, 55(2), 280–294. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spol.12656>
- Bhaskar, S., Nurtazina, A., Mittoo, S., Banach, M., & Weissert, R. (2021). Editorial: Telemedicine During and Beyond COVID-19. In *Frontiers in Public Health* (Vol. 9). Frontiers Media S.A. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.662617>
- Bhatia, R., & Abraham, P. (2022). COVID-19 pandemic: Current & future perspectives. In *Indian Journal of Medical Research* (Vol. 155, Issues 5–6, pp. 445–449). Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijmr.ijmr_1493_22
- Bigoni, A., Malik, A. M., Tasca, R., Baleeiro, M., Carrera, M., Maria, L., Schiesari, C., Gambardella, D. D., & Massuda, A. (2022). *Brazil's health system functionality amidst of the COVID-19 pandemic: An analysis of resilience*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j>
- Binagwaho, A., Hirwe, D., & Mathewos, K. (2022). Health system resilience: withstanding shocks and maintaining progress. *Global Health: Science and Practice*, 10(Supplement 1).
- Bloomstone, S., Fleming, M., Arana, M., D'Angelo, E., Ravenhall, S., & Murrman, M. (2022). COVID-19 Vaccine Administration: Phase 2 of an in Progress Review in New York State Local Health Departments. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(20). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192013030>
- Buchan, J., Williams, G. A., Zapata, T., & Advisor, R. (2021). *GOVERNING HEALTH WORKFORCE RESPONSES DURING COVID-19* (Vol. 27, Issue 1).
- Chang, C. M., Tan, T. W., Ho, T. C., Chen, C. C., Su, T. H., & Lin, C. Y. (2020). COVID-19: Taiwan's epidemiological characteristics and public and hospital responses. *PeerJ*, 2020(6). <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.9360>
- Chhim, S., Ku, G., Mao, S., Van De Put, W., Van Damme, W., Ir, P., Chhea, C., & Or, V. (2023). Descriptive assessment of COVID-19 responses and lessons learnt in Cambodia, January 2020 to June 2022. *BMJ Global Health*, 8(5). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2023-011885>
- Chua, A. Q., Tan, M. M. J., Verma, M., Han, E. K. L., Hsu, L. Y., Cook, A. R., Teo, Y. Y., Lee, V. J., & Legido-Quigley, H. (2020). Health system resilience in managing the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons from Singapore. *BMJ Global Health*, 5(9), e003317. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-003317>
- Coccia, M. (2022). Preparedness of countries to face COVID-19 pandemic crisis: Strategic positioning and factors supporting effective strategies of prevention of pandemic threats. *Environmental Research*, 203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111678>
- Corbin, J. H., Oyene, U. E., Manoncourt, E., Onya, H., Kwamboka, M., Amuyunzu-Nyamongo, M., Sørensen, K., Mweemba, O., Barry, M. M., Munodawafa, D., Bayugo, Y. V., Huda, Q., Moran, T., Omoleke, S. A., Spencer-Walters, D., & Van Den Broucke, S. (2021). A health promotion approach to emergency management: effective community engagement strategies from five cases. *Health Promotion International*, 36, 124–138. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/daab152>

- Desson, Z., Lambert, L., Peters, J. W., Falkenbach, M., & Kauer, L. (2020). Europe's Covid-19 outliers: German, Austrian and Swiss policy responses during the early stages of the 2020 pandemic. *Health Policy and Technology*, 9(4), 405–418. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2020.09.003>
- Desson, Z., Weller, E., McMeekin, P., & Ammi, M. (2020). An analysis of the policy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic in France, Belgium, and Canada. *Health Policy and Technology*, 9(4), 430–446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2020.09.002>
- Djalante, R., Nurhidayah, L., Van Minh, H., Phuong, N. T. N., Mahendradhata, Y., Trias, A., Lassa, J., & Miller, M. A. (2020). COVID-19 and ASEAN responses: Comparative policy analysis. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2020.100129>
- Džakula, A., Banadinović, M., Lovrenčić, I. L., Vajagić, M., Dimova, A., Rohova, M., Minev, M., Scintee, S. G., Vladescu, C., Farcasanu, D., Robinson, S., Spranger, A., Sagan, A., & Rechel, B. (2022). A comparison of health system responses to COVID-19 in Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania in 2020. *Health Policy*, 126(5), 456–464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2022.02.003>
- Dzinamarira, T., Dzobo, M., & Chitungo, I. (2020). COVID-19: A perspective on Africa's capacity and response. In *Journal of Medical Virology* (Vol. 92, Issue 11, pp. 2465–2472). John Wiley and Sons Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.26159>
- Dzinamarira, T., Mapingure, M. P., Rwibasira, G. N., Mukwenha, S., & Musuka, G. (2021). COVID-19: Comparison of the response in Rwanda, South Africa and Zimbabwe. *MEDICC Review*, 23(3), 15–20. <https://doi.org/10.37757/MR2021.V23.N3.4>
- Emahi, I., Watts, M. C., Azibere, S., Morrison, J. F., & Sarpong, K. A. (2021). COVID-19 in Africa: Rethinking the tools to manage future pandemics. *African Health Sciences*, 21(4), 1509–1517. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v21i4.3>
- Fakher, H., & Abiari, E. L. (2020). *MOROCCO'S COVID-19 AFRICAN INITIATIVE: A MIRROR OF COMPLEX ASPIRATIONS*.
- Fawole, O. I., Bello, S., Adebawale, A. S., Bamgboye, E. A., Salawu, M. M., Afolabi, R. F., Dairo, M. D., Namale, A., Kiwanuka, S., Monje, F., Namuhani, N., Kabwama, S., Kizito, S., Ndejjo, R., Seck, I., Diallo, I., Makhtar, M., Leye, M., Ndiaye, Y., ... Wanyenze, R. (2023). COVID-19 surveillance in Democratic Republic of Congo, Nigeria, Senegal and Uganda: strengths, weaknesses and key Lessons. *BMC Public Health*, 23(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15708-6>
- Fleming, P., O'Donoghue, C., Almirall-Sanchez, A., Mockler, D., Keegan, C., Cylus, J., Sagan, A., & Thomas, S. (2022). Metrics and indicators used to assess health system resilience in response to shocks to health systems in high income countries—A systematic review. In *Health Policy* (Vol. 126, Issue 12, pp. 1195–1205). Elsevier Ireland Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2022.10.001>
- Forsgren, L., Tediosi, F., Blanchet, K., & Saulnier, D. D. (2022). Health systems resilience in practice: a scoping review to identify strategies for building resilience. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22(1), 1173.
- Gandhi, P. A., & Hemmati, P. (n.d.). *An overview of Iran's actions in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and in building health system resilience*. <https://sib.behdasht.gov.ir/>

- Gebremeskel, A. T., Otu, A., Abimbola, S., & Yaya, S. (2021). Building resilient health systems in Africa beyond the COVID-19 pandemic response. In *BMJ Global Health* (Vol. 6, Issue 6). BMJ Publishing Group. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2021-006108>
- Ha, B. T. T., Quang, L. N., Mirzoev, T., Tai, N. T., Thai, P. Q., & Dinh, P. C. (2020). Combating the COVID-19 epidemic: Experiences from Vietnam. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *17*(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17093125>
- Haldane, V., De Foo, C., Abdalla, S. M., Jung, A.-S., Tan, M., Wu, S., Chua, A., Verma, M., Shrestha, P., & Singh, S. (2021). Health systems resilience in managing the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons from 28 countries. *Nature Medicine*, *27*(6), 964–980.
- Hunte, S. A., Pierre, K., Rose, R. S., & Simeon, D. T. (2020). Health systems' resilience: COVID-19 response in Trinidad and Tobago. In *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* (Vol. 103, Issue 2, pp. 590–592). American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.20-0561>
- Kavanagh, K. T., Pontus, C., Pare, J., & Cormier, L. E. (2021). COVID-19 lessons learned: a global perspective. *Antimicrobial Resistance and Infection Control*, *10*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13756-021-00992-x>
- Khanna, R. C., Cicinelli, M. V., Gilbert, S. S., Honavar, S. G., & Murthy, G. V. S. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic: Lessons learned and future directions. In *Indian Journal of Ophthalmology* (Vol. 68, Issue 5, pp. 703–710). Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijo.IJO_843_20
- Kuguyo, O., Kengne, A. P., & Dandara, C. (2020). Singapore COVID-19 Pandemic Response as a Successful Model Framework for Low-Resource Health Care Settings in Africa? In *OMICS A Journal of Integrative Biology* (Vol. 24, Issue 8, pp. 470–478). Mary Ann Liebert Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1089/omi.2020.0077>
- Lanyero, B., Edea, Z. A., Musa, E. O., Watore, S. H., Mandalia, M. L., Livinus, M. C., Ebrahim, F. K., Girmay, A., Bategereza, A. K., Abayneh, A., Sambo, B. H., & Abate, E. (2021). Readiness and early response to COVID-19: Achievements, challenges and lessons learnt in Ethiopia. *BMJ Global Health*, *6*(6). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2021-005581>
- Mghamba, J., Gilmour, E., Robinson, L., Simba, A., Tuyishime, A., Persaud, A., Mwansambo, C., Somatunga, L., Werema, S., Mchwampaka, W., Makundi, V., Remedius, K., Ronjiono, F., Mutayoba, B., Dushime, T., Rwagasore, E., Byiringiro, B., Mugumya, S., Muvunyi, C., ... Wadugedara, R. (2023). The use of innovative approaches to strengthen health system resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic: case studies from selected Commonwealth countries. *Frontiers in Public Health*, *11*, 1115415. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1115415>
- Moonasar, D., Pillay, A., Leonard, E., Naidoo, R., Mngemane, S., Ramkrishna, W., Jamaloodien, K., Lebese, L., Chetty, K., Bamford, L., Tanna, G., Ntuli, N., Mlisana, K., Madikizela, L., Modisenyane, M., Engelbrecht, C., Maja, P., Bongweni, F., Furumele, T., ... Pillay, Y. (2021). COVID-19: Lessons and experiences from South Africa's first surge. *BMJ Global Health*, *6*(2). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-004393>

- OECD. (2022). First lessons from government evaluations of COVID-19 responses: A synthesis. <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/governance/first-lessons-from-gover> doi. [10.1787/483507d6-en](https://doi.org/10.1787/483507d6-en)
- Okeke, C., Uzochukwu, B., Onyedinma, C., & Onwujekwe, O. (2022). An assessment of Nigeria's health systems response to COVID-19. *Ghana Medical Journal*, 56(3), 74–84.
- Olu, O. O., Waya, J. L. L., Bankss, S., Maleghemi, S., & Guyo, A. G. (2022). Integrated approaches to COVID-19 emergency response in fragile, conflict-affected and vulnerable settings: a public health policy brief. *Journal of Public Health Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-022-00383-5>
- Peters, M., Godfrey, C. M., Mcinerney, P., & Soares, C. B. (2015). *Methodology for JBI Scoping Reviews*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/294736492>
- Sagan, B. A., Scott, L., Webb, E., Mckee, M., Muscat, N. A., Lessof, S., Mata, I. De, & Figueras, J. (2022). *Strengthening health system resilience in the covid-19 era*. 28(1), 4–8.
- Saikat, S., Dumitra, G., Winkelmann, J., & Ginneken, V. E. (n.d.). *Perspective: Lessons from COVID-19 of countries in the European region in light of findings from the health system response monitor*. <https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/monitors/hcrm/analyses>
- Sundararaman, T., Muraleedharan, V. R., & Ranjan, A. (2021). Pandemic resilience and health systems preparedness: lessons from COVID-19 for the twenty-first century. *Journal of Social and Economic Development*, 23(Suppl 2), 290–300.
- Talisuna, A., Iwu, C., Okeibunor, J., Stephen, M., Musa, E. O., Herring, B. L., Ramadan, O. P. C., Yota, D., Nanyunja, M., Mpairwe, A., Banza, F. M., Diallo, A. B., Wango, R. K., Massidi, C., Njenge, H. K., Traore, M., Oke, A., Bonkougou, B., Mayigane, L. N., ... Gueye, A. S. (2022). Assessment of COVID-19 pandemic responses in African countries: Thematic synthesis of WHO intra-action review reports. In *BMJ Open* (Vol. 12, Issue 5). BMJ Publishing Group. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-056896>
- Tessema, G. A., Kinfu, Y., Dachew, B. A., Tesema, A. G., Assefa, Y., Alene, K. A., Aregay, A. F., Ayalew, M. B., Bezabhe, W. M., Bali, A. G., Dadi, A. F., Duko, B., Erku, D., Gebrekidan, K., Gebremariam, K. T., Gebremichael, L. G., Gebreyohannes, E. A., Gelaw, Y. A., Gesesew, H. A., ... Tesfay, F. H. (2021). The COVID-19 pandemic and healthcare systems in Africa: A scoping review of preparedness, impact and response. *BMJ Global Health*, 6(12). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2021-007179>
- Thomas, S., Sagan, A., Larkin, J., Cylus, J., Figueras, J., & Karanikolos, M. (2020). *Strengthening health systems resilience POLICY BRIEF 36 Key concepts and strategies HEALTH SYSTEMS AND POLICY ANALYSIS*. <http://www.euro.who.int/en/about-us/partners/>
- Thu, K. M., Bernays, S., & Abimbola, S. (2022). A literature review exploring how health systems respond to acute shocks in fragile and conflict-affected countries. In *Conflict and Health* (Vol. 16, Issue 1). BioMed Central Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-022-00484-8>
- Van Ginneken, E., Siciliani, L., Reed, S., Eriksen, A., Tille, F., Zapata, T., & Advisor, R. (2022). ADDRESSING BACKLOGS AND MANAGING WAITING LISTS DURING AND BEYOND THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC. In *Eurohealth* (Vol. 28, Issue 1).

- Wang, X., Shi, L., Zhang, Y., Chen, H., & Sun, G. (2021). Policy disparities in response to COVID-19 between Singapore and China. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-021-01525-z>
- Wang, Z., Duan, Y., Jin, Y., & Zheng, Z. J. (2020). Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic: how countries should build more resilient health systems for preparedness and response. *Global Health Journal*, 4(4), 139–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glohj.2020.12.001>
- Wasswa, J. H., Oundo, H., Oteba, M. O., Komakech, H., Ochola, I., Mwebaze, S., Okidi, D., Kirunda, A., Nakadde, S., Oteba, N. O., Oteba, N. O., & Lugada, E. (2023). Leveraging electronic logistics management information systems to enhance and optimize supply chain response during public health emergencies: lessons from COVID-19 response in Uganda. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40545-023-00517-4>
- Webb, E., Winkelmann, J., Scarpetti, G., Behmane, D., Habicht, T., Kahur, K., Kasekamp, K., Köhler, K., Miščikienė, L., Misins, J., Reinap, M., Slapšinskaitė-Dackevičienė, A., Vörk, A., & Karanikolos, M. (2022). Lessons learned from the Baltic countries' response to the first wave of COVID-19. *Health Policy*, 126(5), 438–445. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2021.12.003>
- Williams, F., Oke, A., & Zachary, I. (2019). Public health delivery in the information age: the role of informatics and technology. *Perspectives in Public Health*, 139(5), 236–254.
- Williams, G. A., Fahy, N., Aissat, D., Lenormand, M.-C., Stüwe, L., Zablitz-Schmidt, I., Delafuys, S., Le Douarin, Y.-M., & Muscat, N. A. (2022). COVID-19 AND THE USE OF DIGITAL HEALTH TOOLS: OPPORTUNITY AMID CRISIS THAT COULD TRANSFORM HEALTH CARE DELIVERY. In *Eurohealth* (Vol. 28, Issue 1).
- Williams, G. A., Maier, C. B., Scarpetti, G., Galodé, J., Lenormand, M.-C., Ptak-Bufken, K., De, I., Mata, L., Scotter, C., & Zapata, T. (2022).) on Health Workforce and Service Delivery. In *Eurohealth* (Vol. 28, Issue 1).
- Williams, G. A., Scarpetti, G., Langins, M., Callies, I., Fourcade, A., Van Ginneken, E., & Maier, C. B. (2022). HUMAN RESOURCES FOR HEALTH DURING COVID-19: SUPPORTING AND PROTECTING HEALTH WORKERS. In *Eurohealth* (Vol. 28, Issue 1).
- Winkelmann, J., Webb, E., Williams, G. A., Hernández-Quevedo, C., Maier, C. B., & Panteli, D. (2022a). European countries' responses in ensuring sufficient physical infrastructure and workforce capacity during the first COVID-19 wave. *Health Policy*, 126(5), 362–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2021.06.015>
- Winkelmann, J., Webb, E., Williams, G. A., Hernández-Quevedo, C., Maier, C. B., & Panteli, D. (2022b). European countries' responses in ensuring sufficient physical infrastructure and workforce capacity during the first COVID-19 wave. *Health Policy*, 126(5), 362–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2021.06.015>
- Zhang, J., Yang, H., Yang, M., & Tan, H. (2022). The role of vaccines in COVID-19 control strategies in Singapore and China. *Health Policy and Technology*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2022.100620>

Zikargae, M. H. (2020). Covid-19 in ethiopia: Assessment of how the ethiopian government has executed administrative actions and managed risk communications and community engagement. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy*, 13, 2803–2810. <https://doi.org/10.2147/RMHP.S278234>

Figure legends

Figure 1. Framework for evaluating COVID-19 responses. (Source: OECD, 2022)

Figure 2: The PRISMA flow chart for systematic reviews was used to illustrate the selection processes.

Table Legend

Table 1: Summary of the thematic analysis

Table 1: Summary of the thematic analysis

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
1. Emergency preparedness			
Disaster Risk Anticipation and Foresight	Strengthening monitoring, surveillance, and early warning systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting risks and vulnerability assessment • Promoting research and development and investing in essential public health functions including those needed for all-hazards emergency risk management • Enhancing surveillance strategies (early case detection, investigation, isolation, and referrals; alert and rumor management, contact tracing, and community-based surveillance) • Decentralizing contact tracing and supporting regional and district teams • Training of Rapid Response Teams for effective operational response • Leveraging technology to facilitate contact tracing efforts and real-time electronic data analysis and transmission • Enhancing data stewardship and data governance systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Williams, Fahy, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Arabi <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Kuguyo <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Abubakar <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gebremeskel, <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Aisyah <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chang <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Fawole <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Wang <i>et al.</i>, 2021a • Moonasar <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Sundararaman <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Binagwaho <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
Emergency protocols	Procedures and guidelines to follow in the event of pandemics or emergencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and implementation of emergency protocols including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Emergency Preparedness and Response Plans (EPRPs), checklists and protocols – Clinical tools and guidelines for infectious disease case management – Guidelines for personal hygiene, surveillance, contact tracing, quarantine, diagnosis, and laboratory tests – Disaster response/management toolkit for scalability and surge capacities – Public health emergency contingency plans for Ports of entry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Hunte <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Zikargae, 2020 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023
Preparedness of critical sectors	National critical infrastructure in anticipation of epidemics and pandemics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening logistics and supply chain management • Expanding national ICU capacity. • Creating strategic reserves of essential equipment and health products • Developing the capacity to produce medical countermeasures for epidemic-prone diseases. • Prioritizing domestic production capacity for medical equipment, pharmaceuticals, vaccines, and drug discovery. • Investing in integrated health infrastructures • Establishing public policies and regulatory frameworks for healthcare digitization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arabi <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • William <i>et al.</i>, 2022c • Balde <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Ven Ginneken <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gebremeskel, <i>et al.</i>, 2021
2: Management of crisis			
Crisis Communication	Communication and engagement with the public and communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timely, transparent, and accurate government communication • Establishment of dedicated hotlines and communication channels • Development of communication materials and apps • Social mobilization and sensitization campaigns through partnerships with CSOs • Monitoring and addressing misinformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Babe <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Ha <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Abubakar <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Al Siyabi <i>et al.</i>, 2021

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder participation and engagement, involving community influencers Forming partnerships with social media companies and mobile network providers to disseminate key health messages. Addressing stigma and resistance through intensive social awareness campaigns Tailoring messages and campaigns to specific populations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Alava & Guevara, 2021 Bloomstone <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Chhim <i>et al.</i>, 2023 Corbin <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Thu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Zikargae, 2020 Moonasar <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Akande <i>et al.</i>, 2023
Governance arrangements	Country-level response coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High-level political leadership and sustained commitment Establishment of the National Steering Committee (NSC) for COVID-19 Activation of NPHEOC Clear chain of command, accountability, and strategic direction Regular media briefings and communication through television, radio, websites, and social media Data-driven decision-making, evidence-informed guidelines, and efficient information management Strengthening coordination platforms and involving relevant sectors (a whole-of-government approach) Development of COVID-19 Preparedness and Response Plans aligned with the National Response Framework Effective governance frameworks emphasizing transparency and accountability Coordinating response beyond national borders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Sagan <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Forsgren <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Fleming <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 Ha <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Hunte <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023 Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Assefa, Woldeyohannes, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Bigoni <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Burke <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Kluge <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Coccia, 2022; Desson, Lambertz, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Desson, Weller, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Djalante <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Tille <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Thu <i>et al.</i>, 2022
Whole-of-Society Response	Institutionalising mechanism for multi-sectoral and multidisciplinary response	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fostering multi-sectoral and multi-disciplinary response <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborating with the private sector, academia, civil societies, etc Partnership with international agencies and organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Aisyah <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Bloomstone <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inclusive engagement of communities through partnership with local leaders and influencers - Transparent communication, collaboration within the health system, and partnerships with external groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Babe <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021
3. Response and recovery			
Lockdown and restrictions	Implementation of containment, isolation, and mitigation measures to reduce the spread of infection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Declaration of a state of emergency and implementation of stringent lockdown measures • Intensive testing and case confirmation • Contact tracing and isolation of infected persons • Enforcement of non-pharmaceutical measures (social distancing, confinement, personal hygiene, handwashing, hand sanitizing, and use of masks in public places). • Environmental disinfection • Ban on public and mass social gatherings • Travel bans (air, road, and sea transportation) • Closure of businesses, industries, and schools • Workplace monitoring and screening for COVID-19 symptoms • Provision of mandatory WASH materials at entrances of work and commercial places 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Khanna <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Kavanagh, <i>et al.</i> 2021 • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Amin Tabish, 2020 • Kuguyo <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Emahi <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Beesley <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Binagwaho <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Chang <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Desson, Weller, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Džakula <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Tille <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Webb, Winkelmann, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Moonasar <i>et al.</i>, 2021
	Ports of Entry (PoEs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closure of national borders • Ensuring compliance with WHO IHR at the PoEs • Strengthening screening and surveillance at PoEs • Case detection, mandatory quarantine, and surveillance reporting for international arrivals • Availability of information, education, and communication materials at PoEs, including thermal scanners and infrared thermometers • PCR tests and rapid antigen tests conducted for inbound and outbound travelers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Kuguyo <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Alava & Guevara, 2021 • Binagwaho <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Tabish, 2020 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Wang <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Wang, <i>et al.</i>, 2020

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
Economic and Financial Support	Financing mechanisms to provide stability of health system and relief for businesses and households	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the uninterrupted flow of funds to support outbreak preparedness and response • Implementation of tax-based measures including tax relief, deferred tax reporting, and income tax payment for individuals and small enterprises • Reduction in interest rates for citizens and businesses and soft loans to local manufacturing companies • Drawing on financial reserves, budget reallocations, and borrowing • Funding support from development partners • Creation of a special fund for COVID-19 response • Increasing budgetary allocations to the health sector • Adapting payment systems to the new environment • Minimizing opportunities for corruption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bhatia & Abraham, 2022 • Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Sagan <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Elbeshbishi <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Fagher & Abiari, 2020 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Desson, Lambertz, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Desson, Weller, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Adebis <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Djalante <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • United Nations, 2021
Social policies	Social protection measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social assistance: cash and other in-kind transfer • Social insurance: health protection, social security, unemployment insurance • Labour market subsidies (special allowances or grants, wage subsidies, leave benefits) • Access to basic services (housing, water, sanitation electricity, education, etc) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hunte <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Baptista <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Iyer <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • United Nations, 2021 • Béland <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Aidukaite_ <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Webb, Winkelmann, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Banda Chitsamatanga & Malinga, 2021

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
Health Measures	Human Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilizing and recruiting additional health workers and volunteers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increasing recruitment quotas. – Utilising final-year medical and nursing students for support. – Bringing back retired health professionals. – Seeking assistance from other countries or organizations. • Scaling-up capacity among the existing health workforce <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Extending working hours and changing contracts. – Temporarily canceling leave and modifying registration requirements. • Protecting health workers from physical, mental, and financial pressures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Implementing hygiene measures in healthcare facilities. – Regular testing to identify and control infections. – Providing financial and social support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sagan <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chua <i>et al.</i> 2020 • Kavanagh, <i>et al.</i> 2021 • Williams, Maier, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Williams, Scarpetti, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Ginneken <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Fleming <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Burau <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Huntet <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Winkelmann, Panteli <i>et al.</i>, 2022; • Winkelmann, Webb, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Assefa, Gilks, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Buchan <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Džakula <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Tille <i>et al.</i>, 2022
	Maintaining essential health service delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skill-mix changes to shift primary care tasks to nurses • Leveraging primary health care for essential services • Introducing new care pathways to reach patients • Providing guidelines for service continuity during outbreaks, • Utilizing the private sector to augment capacity • Implementing teleconsultations and digital health tools to support service delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assaye & Shimie, 2022 • Webb, Lenormand, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Williams, Fahy, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Assefa, Gilks, <i>et al.</i>, 2022
	Case management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment of experts, training, and SOPs • Increasing critical care capacity • Establishing centers for effective clinical management of COVID-19 cases • Home-based isolation and management of COVID-19 cases • Postponing elective treatments and surgeries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Olu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Ha <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Huntet <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Winkelmann, Panteli <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Winkelmann, Webb, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Khanna <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Okeke <i>et al.</i>, 2020

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing hospital networks, both within countries and across borders 	
	Facility-based infection prevention and control (IPC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limiting healthcare facility visits Conducting screening for COVID-19 symptoms Strengthening IPC through capacity building and environmental control. Developing and implementing IPC response plans and guidelines Improving access to WASH services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Olu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Khanna <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Balde <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Abu & Elliott, 2022
	Operational support and logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Block-booking private hospital beds, equipment, and staff to increase capacity Repurposing non-health facilities and establishing temporary facilities to accommodate mild cases Repurposing surgical rooms, anesthesia machines, and clinics for critical care Refurbishing designated hospitals as COVID-19 isolation centers Building purpose-built facilities with integrated functions for infectious disease management Ensuring the appropriate distribution of resources (consumables, devices, and pharmaceuticals) Leveraging technology for efficient resource management Utilizing dedicated global platforms for procurement and logistic support to secure essential equipment, medicines, and supplies Securing support, including donations from local and international organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Olu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Williams, Fahy, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 ven Ginneken <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023 Winkelmann, Panteli <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Winkelmann, Webb, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Hunte <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Alava & Guevara, 2021 Bhaskar <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Džakula <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Wang <i>et al.</i>, 2020 Wasswa <i>et al.</i>, 2023 Webb, Winkelmann <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Moonasar <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Khanna <i>et al.</i>, 2020
	Laboratory diagnosis and management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing and strengthening in-country laboratory networks Implementing a robust system of large-scale testing for epidemic control Leveraging existing laboratory infrastructure and diagnostics industry to expand testing capacity Repurposing research facilities and resources to expand laboratory centers during the pandemic Collaborating with the private sector to enhance testing capabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Tabish, 2020 Balde <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Aisyah <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Tessema <i>et al.</i>, 2021 Tille <i>et al.</i>, 2022 Webb, Winkelmann, <i>et al.</i>, 2022

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decentralizing laboratory capacity through peripheral district laboratories • Shifting from manual RNA extraction to an automated system for quicker results using a pooling system • Leveraging technology to deploy rapid diagnostic tests 	
	Vaccine management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing and implementing vaccination plans and programs • Prioritizing high-risk groups in the initial phase of vaccination efforts • Utilizing the existing primary healthcare supply chain to boost vaccination efforts • Leveraging existing immunization structure to expand vaccination • Fostering partnerships with various stakeholders to expand coverage and enhance vaccine equity • Domestic production of COVID-19 vaccines • Massive advocacy and risk communication to minimize vaccine hesitancy • Utilising digital health tools for the effective rollout of vaccination programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Olu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Williams, Fahy, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Alava & Guevara, 2021 • Amani <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Bloomstone <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Zhang <i>et al.</i>, 2022